

TEACHING SOCIAL-MORAL STANDARDS OF PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION AS A KEY ASPECT OF PEDAGOGY

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Abstract:

This article reflects on the fact that teaching the socio-moral standards of professional-pedagogical activity in students is an urgent problem, on professional orientation, professional standards, as well as on the role of the rules of pedagogical Ethics in mastering the socio-moral standards of professional-pedagogical activity in students.

Key word: professional-pedagogical activity, social moral standard, international standart, professional standard, pedagogical, intellectual potential, higher education, behavior.

As stated in the Decree “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, “Increasing the level of coverage of higher education, training highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking personnel, capable of independent decision-making based on international standards, creating the necessary conditions for their manifestation of intellectual abilities and formation as spiritually mature individuals” has become one of the strategic goals of the development of the higher education system. Socio-ethical norms are of decisive importance in the formation of spiritually mature individuals of pedagogical personnel trained in pedagogical higher education. Currently, increasing the competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions in the labor market, forming in them the professional competence of future teachers, legal, socio-ethical norms for professional and pedagogical activity are considered a functional task of the higher education system and are considered an urgent issue to be studied based on international and national requirements. Students' knowledge of socio-ethical norms and skills in applying them to their activities are a leading component of professional self-improvement and education, and are understood as "pedagogical universal experience, methodological and special knowledge, professional skills and qualifications necessary to improve the pedagogical process, implemented in a specific way in accordance with the goal."

Analysis of scientific literature shows that teaching students socio-ethical norms is relevant from a pedagogical-psychological, socio-humanitarian, normative-legal, theoretical-practical, methodological point of view. The formation of a sense of duty and responsibility in future teachers is associated with the formation of a sense of duty and responsibility in them, and if such qualities and experiences are fully formed in them, then nothing will be an obstacle to acquiring knowledge or professional development. Their knowledge of socio-ethical norms related to professional and pedagogical activity is manifested at the stage of self-identification as a teacher. This stage consists of professional and pedagogical activity, fulfillment of a social role and a socio-psychological system. Self-identification is carried out in

three stages: preparatory, main and final stages. At the preparatory stage, the student identifies the types of activities related to the profession he wants to pursue, clarifies his place and role, justifies and determines his behavior, manners, means and methods of achieving his goals. At the main stage, he realizes the goals of self-realization. At the final stage, the results achieved by the student in the field of self-realization are evaluated, and the causes of difficulties are identified.

Professional and pedagogical success in future teachers is closely related to socio-ethical norms and professional orientation. M.I. Dyachenko, L.A. Kandibovich The development of professional orientation in students is a positive attitude to the future profession, interest in it, strengthening their abilities and skills, the desire to improve their professional and pedagogical activities after graduating from a higher educational institution, satisfying their basic material and spiritual needs during continuous work in the chosen profession, increasing the prestige of the profession in the eyes of the future specialist.

The content of professional orientation is a good knowledge of the future professional activity, obligations, socio-ethical norms, the desire to fulfill their functional duties, to show themselves as a skilled, mature specialist, the desire to clearly solve complex educational tasks and issues, an increased sense of responsibility, and the desire to achieve success in work. Also, the content of professional motives changes with the development of students' attitude to social duty, to themselves, to their aspirations, to their feelings. V.A. Sonin, in his scientific research, emphasized that one of the factors for the successful development of professional orientation in students is the formation of positive motives for choosing a profession.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the status of a teacher is recognized, organizational and legal conditions are being created for them to carry out their professional activities, their social protection is ensured, and guarantees for the implementation of their rights are legally provided. This guarantee is expressed in legislative acts and is reflected in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Status of a Teacher". Ensuring the rights, honor, dignity and professional reputation of a teacher is inextricably linked with the content and process of forming socio-ethical norms in future teachers.

As is known, the professional activity of a teacher is determined by professional standards. The employer, in turn, creates the necessary conditions for the teacher to carry out his professional activities. One of the important components of the professional competence of a teacher is characterized by knowledge of the socio-ethical norms of his activity.

The socio-ethical norms of professional and pedagogical activity can be analyzed from two perspectives. The first is that there are socio-ethical norms established for the activities of teachers in society, and the second is how these socio-ethical norms are formed in pedagogical higher educational institutions, its methodological and conceptual aspects.

If we analyze the process of students choosing modern pedagogical technologies, teaching and upbringing tools and methods, we can see that socio-ethical norms are also important in this process. There are also socio-ethical norms in the development and implementation of author's programs and teaching methodologies related to professional and pedagogical activity, in showing creative activity, as well as in the use of relevant academic disciplines, courses and modules. Participation as a teacher in managing an educational organization, as well as in discussing issues related to the activities of an educational organization, is also reflected in socio-ethical norms.

Teaching social and moral norms in preparing students for professional activity and forming practical skills in this regard is one of the urgent tasks of pedagogical education. For example, there are several social and moral norms in the process of assessing students. Not knowing these norms or not being able to apply them to one's own activities can lead to conflict situations with students, parents, and colleagues. During professional and pedagogical activity, it is a responsible task to independently assess the knowledge of students in the class (group, course) assigned to one, and assessment reflects not only the student's mastery of the subject or cognitive abilities, but also has a number of social and moral aspects. Assessment should objectively reflect the current state of mastery, not to punish the student or thereby convey reflexive information to the student.

The role of communication in the professional and pedagogical activity of a teacher is great. Communication with students and their parents, colleagues, and various government agencies demonstrates the professional identity of the teacher. Professional identity requires strict adherence to the socio-ethical standards of professional pedagogical activity.

The mastery of the norms of protecting one's honor, dignity and professional reputation by professional teachers during the implementation of their professional and pedagogical activities requires a methodological support focused on practice in pedagogical education. Although the socio-ethical norms of professional pedagogical activity are not included in the pedagogical education curriculum as a subject, they are embedded in the content of the subjects of specialized subjects.

In particular, socio-ethical norms are also reflected in the subjects of the subject "Pedagogical Competence". From a didactic point of view, there is an opportunity to embed socio-ethical norms in the content of this subject.

The following can be cited as examples of the widespread application of socio-ethical norms by future educators in the implementation of their professional and pedagogical activities: respecting the honor, dignity and professional reputation of participants in the educational process (students, parents, colleagues, management), increasing the level of knowledge of learners during training sessions, using information and communication technologies, advanced and innovative forms and methods of teaching and upbringing, taking into account the psychological and specific characteristics, physical and mental health, physiological development of learners, paying attention to creating conditions for educating individuals with special educational needs and not discriminating against them, conducting educational work with minor learners in cooperation with their parents or other legal representatives, complying with the charter and other constituent documents of the educational organization, internal labor regulations and pedagogical ethics, mandatory medical timely passing of examinations, etc. The rules of pedagogical ethics are of particular and important importance in the assimilation of socio-ethical norms of professional and pedagogical activity by students. Knowledge and adherence to pedagogical ethics are a criterion that determines the quality indicators of the fulfillment of professional duties by a teacher and the labor discipline of a teacher.

Violation of the rules of pedagogical ethics by a teacher is the basis for bringing him to disciplinary responsibility in accordance with labor legislation. The socio-ethical norms of professional and pedagogical activity are a broad concept and encompass dynamic processes in their content. In the conditions of internationalization and informatization of education, the socio-ethical requirements of activity are also increasing, and these norms are changing and

strengthening under the influence of the socio-cultural life of society. From this perspective, teaching future teachers socio-ethical norms is a pedagogical necessity, and it shows that scientific-methodological, theoretical-conceptual research is necessary.

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